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“MY LIFE AS A WATER CYCLE”

Looking back on my life, I see how much it similar to water cycle, its like an endless flow of change, growth, challenges, struggles, or even success. From a quiet and uncertain moments of being a child to the challenges and struggles I faced today as an adult, I find my life has mirrored the water cycle: evaporation, condensation, precipitation, and collection. Each stage had shaped me, taught me the different lessons of life, and made me for who and what I am today.

In the early years of my life, I was like a water vapor, full of dreams and curiosity. My world was then simple, filled with the warmth and comfort of my Papa and Mama’s love. My parents will work hard and often sacrificing their personal needs just to give us a comfortable life. I did not understand it fully back then, but now I know that their struggles in raising us were the invisible forces that allowed me to rise and to dream, just like water vapor rising into the sky.

As I grew older, I entered the phase of condensation of life, this was the time when the weight of the world began to settle on my shoulders. I entered school- from kindergarten to college, where I faced social pressures because I am different, and I experienced the ups and downs, and the happiness and sadness of growing up. There were moments of joy, excitement, and of hope, but also the challenges that every young person faces. I felt pressure of expectations and even questioning myself, building up like clouds in the sky. I struggled with self-doubt and wondering if I was strong enough to handle the weight of life called “dreams”. But like those clouds that eventually burst into rain, I realized that even the hardest challenges that I might experience, it could bring new beginning. My failures in life became my lessons, my hearth breaks became my strength, and I began to see the value in my journey, that might difficult sometime.

Then came the precipitation of life, the point where I had to face the world head-on. Life was not soft and gentle as the water vapor or the clouds; it’s real, challenging, and or even overwhelming sometime. Like rain falling from the sky, I faced the harsh realities of being an adult. I need to work hard to build my future, often feeling overwhelmed by the responsibilities of school and work. There were days when I felt like a heavy downpour, lost in the flood of emotions, and struggling to stay afloat. But just like rain that nourishes the Earth, my struggles in life taught me to be resilient. It helped me to grow, both as a person and in my ability to weather life’s storms. Each problem, no matter how difficult might be, added a new layer to my character, and I began to understand that I was not just surviving, but I becoming stronger with every drop.

Now, as I reflect on where I am today, I see myself in the collection stage. I have learned to gather the lessons of my life, might be in joy or hardships. Like water flowing into a stream or river, the experiences I have had,

the love, the losses, the triumphs, and the setbacks have all shaped me for who and what I am today. I always think of the sacrifices of my Papa and Mama's made, the way they gave everything so I could have the chance to grow. I always look back to the people who helped me through the toughest moment of my life and the moments of personal achievement where I realized that I was and will be capable of more than I thought. These life experiences have become my stream or river, leading me to the vast ocean of possibilities in the journey of life.

But just like the water cycle, I know that this is not the end. The cycle is ongoing, and I will continue to rise, fall, and rise again. I will face new challenges, new opportunities, and new transformations. Like water, I will always keep moving, always keep flowing. No matter where life takes me, I carry with me the knowledge that every drop, every moment, has led me to this point of life and I will continue to shape my future.

In the end, I see my life as a beautiful water cycle, from the water vapor of childhood dreams, through the condensation of hard lessons of life, to the precipitation of challenges and growth, and now to the collection of all the experiences that made me who I am, as independent and resilient individual. Like water cycle, my journey will never truly end. It will always flow, it will always change, and it will always return to a new beginning.

